

Predicting the Nth Planetary Orbit (Spacetime Curvature); A Practical Application of Dividing by Zero.

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A Practical Application of Dividing by Zero.

In the matter of resolving *non-zero* numbers *divided by zero*, [1] for the Sequence,

$$S_n = \frac{1}{n^2-n}, \dots, \frac{1}{90}, \frac{1}{72}, \frac{1}{56}, \frac{1}{42}, \frac{1}{30}, \frac{1}{20}, \frac{1}{12}, \frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{0},$$

the solution was obtained by finding the Partial Summation S_p of the expression $\frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)}$ at $n = 0$, given as:

$$S_p = \sum_{n=0}^0 \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = \frac{1}{1} = 1$$

So that,

$$\frac{1}{0} = \frac{1}{1} = 1$$

However, the solution to finding its Sum to Infinity, S_i is given as:

$$S_i = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = 2$$

But to find θ , the total inclination angle, subtended by the sequence, S_n from *Zero* into *Infinity*,

$$S_n = \frac{1}{n^2-n}, \dots, \frac{1}{90}, \frac{1}{72}, \frac{1}{56}, \frac{1}{42}, \frac{1}{30}, \frac{1}{20}, \frac{1}{12}, \frac{1}{6}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{0},$$

$$\tan(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = 2$$

$$\tan(\theta) = 2$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(2)$$

$$\theta = 63.43494882^\circ$$

Fig. 1. Illustrating below total angle subtended by sequence from zero into infinity

Molniya Orbits

The angle, $\theta = 63.43494882^\circ$ is the Zero Apogee degree which is the inclination angle of the Molniya orbit.

Consider a Star with a spherical shape. If this spherical Star were inscribed or fit into a rectangular box, forming a Cyclic Quadrilateral with a common centre of origin, then with its diagonal as a Semi-major axis inclined at approximately 63.43° , (Zero Apogee Degree) an elliptical path circumscribing this Cyclic Quadrilateral about its vertices would be measured as the first Planetary Orbit around the Star with its radius as focus. Subsequent Planetary Orbits could be detected along elliptical paths circumscribing vertices of successive Cyclic Quadrilaterals projected outward into the surrounding space-time from from its surface.

Fig. 2. Illustration below showing the orbits around a system host

Fig. 3. Illustration the various orbits around system hosts

Molniya Planetary Orbits in the Solar System

where $\theta = 63.43494882^\circ$,

From:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{\text{Adjacent}}{\text{Hypotenuse}}$$

First Planetary Orbit (P_1)

Given the Radius of the Sun, [21] R_s as 7×10^8 m, at approximately 63.43° the first Planetary Orbit P_1 which is the first orbital distance from the spherical surface of the Sun, would be given as:

$$\text{First Orbit}(P_1) = \frac{\text{Star Radius}(R_s)}{\cos\theta} - \text{Star Radius}(R_s)$$

$$P_1 = \frac{R_s}{\cos\theta} - R_s = R_s(\sec\theta - 1) = R_s(\sqrt{5} - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(\sqrt{5} - 1)$$

Generalization of the N-th Planetary Orbit of Molniya Model.

The *n*-th Orbit, P_n , around the Sun, could be expressed in terms of the preceding Orbit, P_{n-1} as:

$$P_n = P_{n-1}(\sqrt{5})$$

And so where P_{n-1} equals the first Planetary Orbit, P_1 , then the *n*-th Planetary Orbit could be generalized as:

$$P_n = R_s(\sqrt{5} - 1)(\sqrt{5})$$

$$P_n = R_s [(\sqrt{5})^n - (\sqrt{5})^{n-1}]$$

$$P_n = R_s[\sqrt{5} - 1][(\sqrt{5})^{n-1}]$$

Below is a table showing comparative results (in reference to NASA [2] or documented statistics) of Planetary Orbits in the Solar System. Pluto, which is currently classified by the IAU as Dwarf Planet has its orbit also included. It also shows “empty” orbits that are yet to be discovered as hosting celestial bodies around the sun.

Molniya Planetary Orbits Model Comparative Results

PLANETARY ORBIT	NASA/ DOCUMENTED	MOLNIYA	PERCENTAGE ERROR (%)
Orbit 1		8.65×10^8 m	
Orbit 2		1.93×10^9 m	
Orbit 3		4.33×10^9 m	
Orbit 4		9.67×10^9 m	
Orbit 5		2.16×10^{10} m	
Mercury	5.79×10^{10} m	4.84×10^{10} m	16.41 %
Venus	1.08×10^{11} m	1.08×10^{11} m	0 %
Earth	1.50×10^{11} m		
Mars	2.29×10^{11} m	2.42×10^{11} m	13.64 %
Orbit 9		5.41×10^{11} m	
Jupiter	7.42×10^{11} m		
Saturn	1.48×10^{12} m	1.21×10^{12} m	18.24 %
Uranus	2.95×10^{12} m	2.70×10^{12} m	8.47 %
Neptune	4.47×10^{12} m		
Pluto	5.91×10^{12} m	6.05×10^{12} m	2.37 %
Gonggong	1.32×10^{13} m	1.35×10^{13} m	2.27 %
Orbit 14		3.02×10^{13} m	
Orbit 15		6.76×10^{13} m	
Orbit 16		1.51×10^{14} m	

Golden Ratio/Phi (φ) Planetary Orbits Model

The Golden Ratio or *Phi* (φ) is mostly expressed as:

$$\varphi_o = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 0.6180339887$$

And

$$\varphi_1 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.6180339887$$

$$\varphi_o \varphi_1 = 1$$

$$\varphi_1 - \varphi_o = 1$$

Phi-1 (φ_1) Planetary Orbits Model

$$\varphi_1 = 1.6180339887$$

φ_1 is the only number for n that is same as the value of its Partial Summation S_{φ_1} of the expression $\frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)}$ and is given as:

$$S_{\varphi_1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\varphi_1} \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = 1.6180339887$$

The total angle φ_1° subtended when $S_{\varphi_1} = \varphi_1$ could be obtained from:

$$\tan(\varphi_1^\circ) = \sum_{n=0}^{\varphi_1} \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = 1.6180339887$$

$$\tan(\varphi_1^\circ) = 1.6180339887$$

$$\varphi_1^\circ = \tan^{-1}(1.6180339887)$$

$$\varphi_1^\circ = 58.28252559^\circ$$

First Planetary Orbit (P_1)

Where $\varphi_1^\circ = 58.28252559^\circ$ and R_s is Radius of the Sun at 7.00×10^8 m:

$$P_1 = \frac{R_s}{\cos \varphi_1} - R_s = R_s(\sec \varphi_1 - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(\sec \varphi_1 - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(1.902113033 - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(0.902113033)$$

Generalization of the N-th Planetary Orbit of the Phi-1 (ϕ_1) Planetary Orbits Model

In terms of a Preceding Orbit P_{n-1} , a Planetary Orbit could be computed as:

$$P_n = P_{n-1}(1.902113033)$$

And so where the Preceding Orbit, P_{n-1} equals the First Orbit, P_1 , the *n-th* Planetary Orbit P_n of the Phi-1 (ϕ_1) Planetary Orbit Model could be expressed as:

$$P_n = R_s[0.902113033][(1.902113033)^{n-1}]$$

Phi-1 Orbital Model Comparative Results

PLANETARY ORBIT	NASA/ DOCUMENTED	PHI-1	PERCENTAGE ERROR (%)
Orbit 1		6.31×10^8 m	
Orbit 2		1.20×10^9 m	
Orbit 3		2.28×10^9 m	
Orbit 4		4.35×10^9 m	
Orbit 5		8.27×10^9 m	
Orbit 6		1.57×10^{10} m	
Orbit 7		2.99×10^{10} m	
Mercury	5.79×10^{10} m	5.69×10^{10} m	1.73 %
Venus	1.08×10^{11} m	1.08×10^{11} m	0 %
Earth	1.50×10^{11} m		
Mars	2.29×10^{11} m	2.06×10^{11} m	10.04 %
Ceres?	4.13×10^{11} m	3.91×10^{11} m	5.33 %
Jupiter	7.42×10^{11} m	7.45×10^{11} m	0.40 %
Saturn	1.48×10^{12} m	1.42×10^{12} m	4.05 %
Uranus	2.95×10^{12} m	2.69×10^{12} m	8.81 %
Neptune	4.47×10^{12} m	5.12×10^{12} m	12.70 %
Pluto	5.91×10^{12} m	9.75×10^{12} m	39.38 %
Eris	1.10×10^{13} m	1.85×10^{13} m	44.86 %
Gonggong	1.32×10^{13} m	3.53×10^{13} m	62.61 %

Phi-0 (φ_0) Planetary Orbits Model

$$\varphi_0 = 0.6180339887$$

When the Partial Sum, S_{φ_0} of the expression $\frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)}$ equals **0.6180339887**

$$S_{\varphi_0} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)}{(n+1)} = 0.6180339887$$

The angle, φ_0° subtended by the diagonal in the Phi-0 (φ_0) Planetary Orbits Model could be computed as:

$$\varphi_0^\circ = \tan^{-1}(0.6180339887)$$

$$\varphi_0^\circ = 31.71747441^\circ$$

First Planetary Orbit (P_1)

Where $\varphi_0^\circ = 31.71747441^\circ$ and R_s is Radius of the Sun at 7.00×10^8 m.

$$P_1 = \frac{R_s}{\cos\varphi_0} - R_s = R_s(\sec\varphi_0 - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(1.175570505 - 1)$$

$$P_1 = R_s(0.175570505)$$

Generalization of the N-th Planetary Orbit of the Phi-1 (φ_1) Model

If the preceding Orbit P_{n-1} of an orbit could be related to any Orbit P_n , as:

$$P_n = P_{n-1}(1.175570505)$$

Then where the preceding orbit, P_{n-1} equals the first orbit, P_1 , the **n-th** Planetary Orbit P_n of the Phi-0 (φ_0) Planetary Orbit Model could be computed as:

$$P_n = R_s[0.175570505][(1.175570505)^{n-1}]$$

Phi-0 Planetary Orbits Model Comparative Results

Orbits	NASA/ Documented	Phi-0	% Error
Orbit 1		6.19×10^8 m	
Orbit 2		1.18×10^9 m	
Orbit 3		2.26×10^9 m	
Orbit 4		4.32×10^9 m	
Orbit 5		8.24×10^9 m	
Orbit 6		1.57×10^{10} m	
Orbit 7		3.00×10^{10} m	
Mercury	5.79×10^{10} m	5.74×10^{10} m	0.84 %
Venus	1.08×10^{11} m	1.09×10^{11} m	0.92 %
Earth	1.50×10^{11} m	1.52×10^{11} m	1.32 %
Mars	2.29×10^{11} m	2.09×10^{11} m	10.04 %
Orbit 11/ Ceres	4.13×10^{11} m	4.00×10^{11} m	3.15 %
Jupiter	7.42×10^{11} m	7.64×10^{11} m	2.88 %
Saturn	1.48×10^{12} m	1.46×10^{12} m	1.35 %
Uranus	2.95×10^{12} m	2.80×10^{12} m	5.08 %
Neptune	4.47×10^{12} m	4.52×10^{12} m	1.11%
Pluto	5.91×10^{12} m	5.32×10^{12} m	9.98 %
Eris	1.02×10^{13} m	9.75×10^{12} m	2.70 %
Gonggong	1.32×10^{13} m	1.40×10^{13} m	5.71 %

Below are found tabular analyses of the **Phi-Molniya** Planetary Orbits Model compared to observations from NASA.

Orbits	Molniya	NASA	Phi-1	Phi-0
Mercury	4.84×10^{10} m	5.79×10^{10} m	5.69×10^{10} m	5.74×10^{10} m
Venus	1.08×10^{11} m	1.08×10^{11} m	1.08×10^{11} m	1.09×10^{11} m
Earth		1.50×10^{11} m		1.52×10^{11} m
Mars	2.42×10^{11} m	2.29×10^{11} m	2.06×10^{11} m	2.09×10^{11}
Ceres?	5.41×10^{11} m	4.13×10^{11} m	3.91×10^{11} m	4.00×10^{11} m
Jupiter		7.42×10^{11} m	7.45×10^{11} m	7.64×10^{11} m
Saturn	1.21×10^{12} m	1.48×10^{12} m	1.42×10^{12} m	1.46×10^{12} m
Uranus	2.70×10^{12} m	2.95×10^{12} m	2.70×10^{12} m	2.80×10^{12} m
Neptune		4.47×10^{12} m		4.52×10^{12} m
Pluto	6.05×10^{12} m	5.91×10^{12} m	5.12×10^{12} m	5.32×10^{12} m
Eris		1.02×10^{13} m	9.75×10^{12} m	1.02×10^{13} m
Gonggong	1.35×10^{13} m	1.32×10^{13} m	1.85×10^{13} m	1.40×10^{13} m

Orbit	Molniya	NASA	Phi-1	Phi-0
Mercury	16.41 %	5.79×10^{10} m	1.73 %	0.84 %
Venus	0 %	1.08×10^{11} m	0 %	0.92 %
Earth		1.50×10^{11} m		1.32 %
Mars	13.64 %	2.29×10^{11} m	10.04 %	8.73 %
Ceres?	23.66 %	4.13×10^{11} m	5.33 %	3.15 %
Jupiter		7.42×10^{11} m	0.40 %	2.88 %
Saturn	18.24 %	1.48×10^{12} m	4.05 %	1.35 %
Uranus	8.47 %	2.95×10^{12} m	8.81 %	5.08 %
Neptune		4.47×10^{12} m	12.70 %	1.11%
Pluto	2.37 %	5.91×10^{12} m	39.38 %	9.98 %
Eris		1.02×10^{13} m	44.86 %	0 %
Gonggong	2.27 %	1.32×10^{13} m	62.61 %	5.71 %

Molniya Orbits	Phi-1 Orbits	Phi-0 Orbits
		Mercury
Venus	Venus	Venus
		Earth
		Mars
		Ceres
	Jupiter	
		Saturn
		Uranus
		Neptune
Pluto		
		Eris
Gonggong		

Molniya Orbits	Phi Orbits
	Mercury
Venus	Venus
	<i>Earth</i>
	Mars
	Ceres
	Jupiter
	Saturn
Uranus	Uranus
	<i>Neptune</i>
Pluto	
	Eris
Gonggong	

Implications

1. The Orbits of the celestial bodies around a host Star or the Sun are identical to or follow certain elliptical curvature(s) of spacetime that are geometrically predetermined by the size of the radius/circumference/volume of their host Stars/Sun and the model angles, and not the mass of the host Star or Sun perse. For example, if two stars had the same radii sizes and all other specifications in common except their masses, the observation would be that the spacetime curvature their orbiting Planets follow would all be the same, except that the massive star would have its planets orbiting faster than the less massive star. This might not be different for Black Holes or Supermassive Black Holes.
2. All orbits have a solid focus or locus that traces the circumference of host Stars radial to their orbital planes.
3. The angles, θ , φ_0 , and φ_1 could be very fundamental to describing or predicting the shape of the Universe itself.
4. Each **Phi-0** orbital is mostly consisted of correspondent **Phi-1** orbitals with three degenerate orbitals each. And so the **Earth**'s Orbit is actually the second (2nd) order degenerate orbit of **Venus**. whiles **Neptune** is the third (3rd) order degenerate Orbit of **Uranus**. **Gonggong** which is a **Molniya Orbit** however comes across as the second (2nd) order degenerate Orbit of **Eris** which is a **Phi-0 Orbit**. And this shows that **Molniya Orbits** and **Phi-0** and **Phi-1** all form an inseparable model, the **Phi-Molniya Model**. And so celestial bodies orbiting stars might simply be classified by their Orbital Models.

5. Also, **Dwarf Planets** like **Ceres, Pluto, Eris, and Gonggong** whose orbits like the **Major Planets** are all predicted by the **Phi-Molniya Model** might not differ substantially from the **Major Planets**. If peradventure Mercury and Pluto switched orbits; that is, replacing Mercury with Pluto, placing it (Mercury) where now Pluto is. In such a scenario, might Mercury be able to clear Pluto's current neighbourhood? if Clearing neighbourhood is one of the three classification criteria [3] for **Major Planets**?
6. The Phi-Molniya Planetary Orbit Model or others derived by modifying some parameters (especially the model angles) could be instrumental to efficiently discovering exo-planets, black holes and other cosmic or celestial bodies and phenomena as well as Extra-Terrestrial Intelligence.
7. When **Phi-1**, and **Phi-0** Orbits are merged and then compared and contrasted to the **Molniya** Orbits, there seems to be a considerable indication that there might be some **Intelligent life form** on **Neptune**. Comparing the Atmosphere of **Neptune**, mainly composed of two gasses that are successive Proton Numbers across the IUPAC Periodic Table that is, **Hydrogen** and **Helium**, with **Earth's** atmosphere which is mainly composed of **Nitrogen** and **Oxygen**, which are also successive Atomic Numbers across the IUPAC Periodic Table, these two types of atmospheres occupying six (6) neighbouring periods (Atomic Numbers) across from each other on the IUPAC Periodic table. So then if the bones of Earthlings are composed of **Calcium**, (with Atomic Number 20) then the bones of such **Intelligent life form** could be composed of **Silicon** (Atomic Number 14=20-6) and they may be dependent on **Helium** and not **Oxygen** for their respiration.

References

1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7275335>
2. <https://nssdc.gsfc.nasa.gov/planetary/factsheet/index.html>
3. <https://www.iau.org/public/themes/pluto/>